

The Space and Time Continuum Model

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Abstract

This study presents the Space and Time Continuum Model, a local formulation of relativistic kinematics. The model results from the limiting condition of a finite local measurement process of space and time in homogeneous and isotropic media and quantifies into an initial value problem incorporating four space and time advection equations. The advection equations' general non-linear solutions, obtained by the method of characteristics, represent space and time flow as invariant-profile space and time waves. As spatial and temporal transformations, the general solutions shape into linear ones that reflect the current formulation of space and time measurement, distinguishing between stationary and moving reference frames. That distinction eliminates itself with additional consideration of the measurement process, proving that inertial reference frames, as aggregates of synchronized clocks where the law of inertia is valid, are equivalent in measuring space and time through a set of extended Poincare transformations. Furthermore, the derivation of the characteristic curves of those transformations completes their interpretation as pairs of space and time waves with constant amplitude and opposite constant phases along those curves. Thus, the Space and Time Continuum Model interprets current relativistic kinematics and broadens the theory by deriving the extended Poincare transformations.

Keywords— Synchronization process, Space and time advection equations, Space and time flow, Extended Poincare transformations

1 Introduction

Space and time measurement proceeds with axioms regarding the invariance of natural laws and the finite constant speed of light propagation in inertial reference frames [1]. Its immediate result is the Lorentz transformations [1, 2, 3], which are linear relations between the spatial and temporal coordinates of inertial reference frames. Lorentz transformations were initially deduced from the requirement that a change of variables for their solution and the constancy of the speed of light preserves Maxwell's equations' [4] covariance between inertial reference frames [2, 5]. In the axiomatic approach, the transformations result from calculating light's spatial and temporal propagation intervals connecting events and identifying them with the events' spatial and temporal coordinates measured by rulers and clocks [1, 6]. However, as that identification is not justified, the derived Lorentz transformations lack an interpretation as space and time transformations.

Early approaches in space and time measurement used a clock synchronization process in homogeneous and isotropic media that defined space and time in inertial reference frames. There were two fundamental approaches in that direction. First, Poincare defined synchronization by correcting time reading delay between clocks and conjectured that the Lorentz transformations are derivable from the proposed synchronization [7]. That approach incorporates local space and time measurement but needs a complete calculational framework. Second, Einstein [1] defined clock synchronization as the time equality of the bidirectional light propagation between two clocks' positions. Hence, it does not locally define space and time measurement.

This study introduces a clock synchronization process extending Poincare's synchronization [7] and locally determining events' space and time. It results in a continuum model of space and time, a local formulation of

relativistic kinematics in inertial reference frames. The model quantifies as an initial value problem incorporating four space and time advection equations with general non-linear solutions. When confined as space and time transformations, the general solutions become linear and form an extended set of Poincare transformations representing space and time waves.

2 Synchronous clocks

If we measure time by local clocks [7, 8], the problem of comparing the times of events that occur in different places arises. Because a clock measures time locally, an experimenter would synchronize the clocks in different places in advance. The synchronization of the clocks means that the consecutive positions of their hands are consistently corresponding during their operation. Thus, when operating at the same rate, we could synchronize two clocks in the same place and transfer them to their preset positions. However, this situation may not accurately synchronize the clocks as we need to know the influence of speed and acceleration on their operating rate.

Poincaré [9] considered light as a distinct signal since its velocity in a homogeneous and isotropic medium is constant in all directions regardless of the motion of its source [10]. By transmitting information from one clock to another by light signals, we can synchronize clocks in different places and avoid the effects of their displacement on their operating rate. Necessarily, the light travel time between clocks would make them appear as having different readings: [9]

When station B receives the signal from station A, its clock must not record at the same time as station A sends the signal, but there is a time increment by a constant representing the duration of the transmission.

Poincaré's condition implies that if one station records a difference in clock readings equal to the light path time between them, the clocks indicate the same time. Further, the clocks synchronize if successive recordings constantly measure the same clock reading differences. In that case, clock synchronization conforms with the basic definition that two clocks synchronize if they have the same initial time and record equal time consistently. The following section describes a synchronization process that incorporates Poincaré's synchronization condition.

2.1 A clock synchronization process

Consider two clocks A and B , which are stationary to a system k at the same position and have the same operating rate, as we can ascertain by comparing their readings. Also, assume they have the same operating rate in a medium at each position. Thus, the medium does not affect their operating rate regarding their place, a property called homogeneity of the medium.

We first describe how clock B synchronizes with clock A , a preset distance r_{AB} from B in the inertial reference frame under construction. Initially, we place the two clocks still not in operation at the same position and set clock B to time τ_B and clock A to the time,

$$\tau_{AB} = \tau_B - \frac{r_{AB}}{c_{AB}}, \quad (1)$$

where c_{AB} is the velocity of light in the direction from A to B . When we move A to a position in the distance r_{AB} from B , clock A starts when it emits a light signal towards B , and B starts when the light signal comes to it. By this process, A and B have the same initial operating time since, by the time the light signal comes to B , B will start with time τ_B given by,

$$\tau_B = \tau_{AB} + \frac{r_{AB}}{c_{AB}}$$

which is the time A has at that moment. Furthermore, if clock B synchronizes with clock A , then clock B will steadily see A 's time differing by

$$\tau_B - \tau_{AB} = \frac{r_{AB}}{c_{AB}}. \quad (2)$$

We have described a procedure by which we synchronized a clock B with a clock A . We repeat the same procedure to synchronize clock A with clock B . Consider the two clocks are initially in the position of A and set clock A at the time τ_A and clock B at the time,

$$\tau_{BA} = \tau_A - \frac{r_{BA}}{c_{BA}}, \quad (3)$$

(where c_{BA} is the velocity of light in the direction from B to A) before moving it to the position previously held by the same clock, a distance r_{BA} from A . A light synchronizing signal starts from clock B , sets it in operation, and travels towards clock A , which sets it in operation when it reaches its position. Then, clocks A and B have the same initial operating time by the time the light signal from clock B arrives at clock A since clock A will start at the time,

$$\tau_A = \tau_{BA} + \frac{r_{BA}}{c_{BA}}, \quad (4)$$

which is the time the clock B has at that time. Furthermore, if clock A synchronizes with clock B , an observer at the position of A will steadily see the time of A differing from the time of clock B by,

$$\tau_A - \tau_{BA} = \frac{r_{BA}}{c_{BA}}. \quad (5)$$

We have described a procedure where a clock A synchronizes with a clock B and clock B synchronizes with clock A . Then, the time differences in (2) and (5) are equal,

$$\tau_B - \tau_{AB} = \tau_A - \tau_{BA} \quad (6)$$

when,

$$\frac{r_{AB}}{c_{AB}} = \frac{r_{BA}}{c_{BA}}. \quad (7)$$

Thus equation (7) implies that when light takes equal time to travel from A to B as for the reverse root, then by equation (6), observers at A and B record similar time differences between the clock at their vicinity and the distant one. Moreover, since we set the clocks at an equal initial time and have the same operating rate, by equation (6), they record the same time during their operation. Thus, the clocks' operation satisfies the two criteria of the basic definition of synchronization, meaning they are synchronous.

2.2 Clock synchronization requests a homogeneous and isotropic medium

From equation (7) the conditions $r_{AB} = r_{BA}$ and, $c_{AB} = c_{BA}$ should apply. Thus, the measured distance between two synchronized clocks and the speed of light is bidirectionally equal, meaning that the medium is isotropic. Additionally, if clocks are synchronizable, then the medium must be homogeneous. Thus, clocks in a medium are synchronizable when the medium is homogeneous and isotropic.

2.3 Inertial reference frames

For locally measuring the spatial and temporal events' coordinates, we consider synchronized clocks in a homogeneous and isotropic medium stationary to each other. Then, a clock at a particular position can read an event's space and time coordinates at the same position. Distant synchronized clocks from the event record the same time as the local clock to the event. Arbitrary events' spatial and temporal coordinates mapping to orthogonal axes define a Cartesian reference frame. Further, moving aggregates of clocks, stationary to each other, map their readings and positions to moving Cartesian reference frames.

The local space and time measurement means that a stationary Cartesian reference frame can measure a moving frame's spatial and temporal coordinates by recording each clock's reading and position by one of its clocks at the corresponding position. Furthermore, we consider that the law of inertia [11] is valid in Cartesian reference frames. Then, necessarily, those frames should move with constant speed relative to each other. For terminology reasons, we rename a Cartesian reference frame as an inertial reference frame. In the following, we use that definition to determine the clocks' readings and positions between those frames.

Figure 1: A stationary to system k observer B at $\xi_{B'}$ reads A 's time with time delay, different from that an observer records at the corresponding position $x_{B'}$ in the system K .

3 Asynchronous clocks and non-equidistant coordinates

This section considers the recordings by an inertial reference frame K of the time and position measurements of clocks stationary in a similar moving frame k . Our findings match Einstein's findings that a system K does not read synchronized clocks stationary to a moving system k as synchronized [1]. Additionally, we find that frame K records equidistant coordinates stationary in the moving frame k as non-equidistant.

3.1 Synchronized clocks' readings and positions in a moving frame

Consider that a frame k moves relative to a second frame K at a constant speed v to the right (see Fig. 1 and Fig. 2). Clocks A and B stationary to k have a distance between them equal to x' as measured in K and synchronize in the two frames as described in subsection (2.1).

First, we consider the condition that clock B synchronizes with clock A in k and how frame K measures the coordinates and readings of the two clocks. In Fig. 1, clock A has time τ_{AB} in k at position ξ_A and a clock in the corresponding position x_A in K reads A 's time to be $t_{AB'}$. Since clock B in k reads A 's time with a time delay equal to the light path time $(\xi_{B'} - \xi_A)/c$, then the corresponding time delay between the reading of the clock x_A by the clock at position $x_{B'}$ in K is $(x_{B'} - x_A)/c$. Thus the observed difference from the clock reading $t_{B'}$ at position $x_{B'}$ to the clock reading $t_{AB'}$ at position x_A is,

$$t_{B'} - t_{AB'} = \frac{x_{B'} - x_A}{c}. \quad (8)$$

The same space and time differences also satisfy,

$$x_{B'} - x_A = x' + v(t_{B'} - t_{AB'}), \quad (9)$$

since in the time delay $t_{B'} - t_{AB'}$ the system k moves a distance $v(t_{B'} - t_{AB'})$ to the right. On substituting the position difference $x_{B'} - x_A$ from (9) to (8) we obtain,

$$t_{B'} = t_{AB'} + \frac{x'}{c - v}, \quad (10)$$

and the time difference $t_{B'} - t_{AB'}$ from (8) in (9) we obtain,

$$x_{B'} = x_A + \frac{cx'}{c - v}. \quad (11)$$

Correspondingly, we consider the condition that clock A synchronizes with clock B in k and how frame K

Figure 2: A stationary to system k observer A at $\xi_{A'}$ reads B 's time with time delay, different from that an observer records at the corresponding position $x_{A'}$ in the system K .

measures the coordinates and readings of the two clocks. In Fig. 2, clock B has time τ_{BA} in k at position ξ_B and a clock in the corresponding position x_B in K reads B 's time to be $t_{BA'}$. Since clock A in k reads B 's time with a time delay equal to the light path time $(\xi_{A'} - \xi_B)/c$, then the corresponding time delay between the reading of the clock x_B by the clock at position $x_{A'}$ is $(x_{A'} - x_B)/c$. Thus the observed difference from the clock reading $t_{A'}$ at position $x_{A'}$ to the clock reading $t_{BA'}$ at position x_B is,

$$t_{A'} - t_{BA'} = \frac{x_{A'} - x_B}{-c}. \quad (12)$$

The same space and time coordinates also satisfy,

$$x_{A'} = x_A + v(t_{A'} - t_{BA'}),$$

since in the time delay $t_{A'} - t_{BA'}$ the system k moves a distance $v(t_{A'} - t_{BA'})$ to the right. The value of x_B in terms of x_A is,

$$x_B = x_A + x'.$$

Substituting the value of x_A in this expression to the previous one we obtain,

$$x_{A'} - x_B = -x' + v(t_{A'} - t_{BA'}) \quad (13)$$

Then, solving the system of equations (12) and (13) for $t_{A'} - t_{BA'}$ and $x_{A'} - x_B$ we obtain,

$$t_{A'} = t_{BA'} + \frac{x'}{c + v}. \quad (14)$$

and,

$$x_{A'} = x_B - \frac{cx'}{c + v}. \quad (15)$$

3.2 Clock non-synchronicity between inertial frames

Condition (6) expresses clock synchronization in the moving inertial frame k . We can calculate the corresponding relation in the stationary frame K by eliminating the auxiliary variable x' from equations (10) and (14),

$$(c - v)(t_{B'} - t_{AB'}) = (c + v)(t_{A'} - t_{BA'}). \quad (16)$$

Thus, the stationary frame K perceives the synchronized clocks in k as non-synchronized. Hence, if the frame k measures two events as simultaneous by its synchronized clocks, frame K measures them as non-simultaneous [1].

3.3 Non-equidistant measurement between inertial reference systems

The necessity of isotropic medium for the clock synchronization implied that the distance that an observer in the frame k at position B measures from A is equal to the distance an observer at A measures from B ,

$$r_{AB} = -r_{BA},$$

or in the symbolism of Fig. 1 and Fig. 2,

$$\xi_B - \xi_A = -(\xi_{A'} - \xi_{B'}).$$

In the frame k the space and time coordinates do not differentiate between the primed and the unprimed ones. Therefore, in the above expression we can exchange between ξ_A and $\xi_{A'}$, and thus obtain,

$$\xi_{B'} - \xi_A = \xi_B - \xi_{A'}. \quad (17)$$

However, when eliminating x' from equations (11) and (15) we obtain,

$$(c - v)(x_{B'} - x_A) = (c + v)(x_B - x_{A'}), \quad (18)$$

which states that an observer in K at position B measures a different distance from position A than an observer at A from B .

4 Space and time advection equations from the synchronization conditions

The previous section derived four finite conditions between spatial and temporal coordinates of events at a distance, within and among inertial reference frames. The infinitesimal limit of those conditions would potentially obtain four corresponding spatial and temporal coordinate relations between inertial reference frames for a local event.

In the following, we use a procedure by which the coordinates in one condition in one reference system are functions of the corresponding coordinates in another [1]. Hence, to obtain an event's spatial and temporal coordinate transformations, we take the infinitesimal limit of variable x' , which denotes the distance between events in the four conditions in frame k as measured by frame K . The outcome is four first-order partial differential equations and their inverses, being space and time advection equations.

4.1 The space advection equation from the equidistant measurement condition

Equation (17),

$$\xi_{B'} - \xi_A = \xi_B - \xi_{A'},$$

becomes,

$$\xi(x_{B'}, t_{B'}) - \xi(x_A, t_{AB'}) = \xi(x_B, t_{BA'}) - \xi(x_{A'}, t_{A'}) \quad (19)$$

when we substitute the corresponding variables in K .

The position of the clock at A' to position B is given by (15),

$$x_{A'} = x_B - \frac{cx'}{c+v}.$$

For $x_B = x_A + x'$,

$$x_{A'} = x_A + \frac{vx'}{c+v}, \quad (20)$$

which denotes $x_{A'}$ in terms of the frame's K origin.

If we substitute the temporal variables' values $t_{A'}$ and $t_{B'}$ from (10) and (14) and the spatial variables' values $x_{B'}$ and $x_{A'}$ from (11) and (20), we obtain,

$$\xi\left(x_A + \frac{cx'}{c-v}, t_{AB'} + \frac{x'}{c-v}\right) - \xi(x_A, t_{AB'}) = \xi(x_A + x', t_{BA'}) - \xi\left(x_A + \frac{vx'}{c+v}, t_{BA'} + \frac{x'}{c+v}\right). \quad (21)$$

By applying the differentiation rule,

$$\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'} = \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} \frac{\partial x}{\partial x'} + \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial t} \frac{\partial t}{\partial x'},$$

on every term of equation (21) we obtain the first order partial differential equation,

$$\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial t} + v \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} = 0. \quad (22)$$

Equation (22) is a particular type of transport equation called the advection equation or the one-way wave equation. In the present case, it is an advection equation of the space coordinates of the moving frame k to the space and time coordinates of the stationary frame K .

4.2 The time advection equation from the clock synchronicity condition

The synchronicity condition equation (6) in the symbolism of Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 takes the form,

$$\tau_{B'} - \tau_{AB} = \tau_{A'} - \tau_{BA}.$$

By substituting the corresponding variables in the system K in the above expression, we obtain,

$$\tau(x_{B'}, t_{B'}) - \tau(x_A, t_{AB'}) = \tau(x_{A'}, t_{A'}) - \tau(x_B, t_{BA'}), \quad (23)$$

The substitution of the variables' values from equations (11) and (20) for the spatial and (10) and (14) for the temporal coordinates, gives,

$$\tau\left(x_A + \frac{cx'}{c-v}, t_{AB'} + \frac{x'}{c-v}\right) - \tau(x_A, t_{AB'}) = \tau\left(x_A + \frac{vx'}{c+v}, t_{BA'} + \frac{x'}{c+v}\right) - \tau(x_A + x', t_{BA'}). \quad (24)$$

If we apply the differentiation rule,

$$\frac{\partial \tau}{\partial x'} = \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial x} \frac{\partial x}{\partial x'} + \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial t} \frac{\partial t}{\partial x'}$$

on every term of equation (24) we obtain the partial differential equation,

$$\frac{\partial \tau}{\partial x} + \frac{v}{c^2} \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial t} = 0.^1 \quad (25)$$

In this form, equation (25) is an advection equation of the moving system's k time coordinate to the stationary system's K space and time coordinates. It is a particular advection equation in that the roles of the independent space and time variables reverse.

¹Einstein [1] obtained a similar equation whose linear solution is not the Lorentz transformation. Instead, the transformation with undetermined Lorentz factor follows from (25) with the linear substitution $\tau = at + bx$.

4.3 The inverse space advection equation from the non-equidistant measurement condition

By substituting the corresponding space and time variables in the system k in condition (18),

$$(c - v)(x_{B'} - x_A) = (c + v)(x_B - x_{A'}),$$

we obtain,

$$(c - v)[x(\xi_{B'}, 0, 0, \tau_{B'}) - x(\xi_A, 0, 0, \tau_{AB})] = (c + v)[x(\xi_B, 0, 0, \tau_{BA}) - x(\xi_{A'}, 0, 0, \tau_{A'})],$$

which by substitution of the variables' values, gives,

$$(c - v) \left[x \left(\xi', 0, 0, \frac{\xi'}{c} \right) - x(\xi_A, 0, 0, \tau_{AB}) \right] = (c + v) \left[x(\xi', 0, 0, \tau_{BA}) - x \left(\xi_A, 0, 0, \frac{\xi'}{c} \right) \right], \quad (26)$$

where ξ' is the distance of the clocks the system k measures, and ξ'/c is the time delay a clock in k reads another clock in the same frame at that distance. By applying the differentiation rule,

$$\frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi'} = \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \xi'} + \frac{\partial x}{\partial \tau} \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial \xi'}$$

on every term of equation (26) we obtain the inverse space advection equation,

$$\frac{\partial x}{\partial \tau} - v \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi} = 0. \quad (27)$$

4.4 The inverse time advection equation from the clock non-synchronicity condition

Lastly, by substituting the corresponding space and time variables in the system k in the non-synchronicity condition (16),

$$(c - v)(t_{B'} - t_{AB'}) = (c + v)(t_{A'} - t_{BA'}),$$

we obtain,

$$(c - v) [t(\xi_{B'}, 0, 0, \tau_{B'}) - t(\xi_A, 0, 0, \tau_{AB})] = (c + v) [t(\xi_{A'}, 0, 0, \tau_{A'}) - t(\xi_B, 0, 0, \tau_{BA})]$$

which, by substitution of the variable's values, gives,

$$(c - v) \left[t \left(\xi', 0, 0, \frac{\xi'}{c} \right) - t(\xi_A, 0, 0, \tau_A) \right] = (c + v) \left[t \left(\xi_A, 0, 0, \frac{\xi'}{c} \right) - t(\xi', 0, 0, \tau_{BA}) \right]. \quad (28)$$

By applying the differentiation rule,

$$\frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi'} = \frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \xi'} + \frac{\partial t}{\partial \tau} \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial \xi'}$$

we obtain the inverse time advection equation,

$$\frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi} - \frac{v}{c^2} \frac{\partial t}{\partial \tau} = 0. \quad (29)$$

5 The solutions of the space and time advection equations

This section derives the general solutions of the space and time advection equations by the method of characteristics [12].

5.1 The general solution of the space advection equation

Equation (22),

$$\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial t} + v \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} = 0, \quad (30)$$

and the initial condition,

$$\xi(x, 0) = \xi_o(x),$$

constitute an initial value problem. If $x = x(t)$ defines a smooth curve C on the (x, t) plane, we find the total derivative of $\xi(x(t), t)$ along the curve by the chain rule,

$$\frac{d\xi}{dt} = \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} \frac{dx}{dt}. \quad (31)$$

Comparing equation (30) to (31), we observe that its right-hand side is the total derivative of ξ ,

$$\frac{d\xi}{dt} = 0$$

along the curves,

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = v. \quad (32)$$

Thus, ξ is constant along the curves,

$$x - vt = \kappa, \quad (33)$$

called the characteristic curves, and κ is the constant of the integration.

A curve defined by equation (33) through an arbitrary point (x, t) intersects the t -axis at $(\kappa, 0)$. Since ξ is constant on this curve, its value $\xi(x, t)$ equals its value $\xi(\kappa, 0)$ at the initial time. Thus, we obtain,

$$\xi(x, t) = \xi(\kappa, 0) = \xi_o(\kappa) = \xi_o(x - vt), \quad (34)$$

which is the general solution to the initial value problem. It represents a space flow as a traveling waveform of invariant profile ξ_o with a speed equal to v , in the direction of increasing x .

5.2 The general solution of the time advection equation

Next, consider equation (25),

$$\frac{\partial \tau}{\partial x} + \frac{v}{c^2} \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial t} = 0,$$

and the initial condition,

$$\tau(0, t) = \tau_o(t).$$

If $t = t(x)$ defines a smooth curve C on the (x, t) plane, we find the total derivative of $\tau(x, t(x))$ along the curve by using the chain rule,

$$\frac{d\tau}{dx} = \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial t} \frac{dt}{dx}.$$

On comparing equation (25) with this expression, we observe that its right-hand side is the total derivative of τ ,

$$\frac{d\tau}{dx} = 0,$$

along the characteristic curves,

$$\frac{dt}{dx} = \frac{v}{c^2}. \quad (35)$$

Thus τ is constant along the characteristic curve,

$$t - \frac{vx}{c^2} = \lambda, \quad (36)$$

with λ being the constant of integration. A characteristic curve passing through an arbitrary point (x, t)

intersects the x -axis at $(0, \lambda)$. Since τ is constant on this curve, its value $\tau(x, t)$ equals its value $\tau(0, \lambda)$ at the initial time. Thus, we obtain,

$$\tau(x, t) = \tau(0, \lambda) = \tau_o(\lambda) = \tau_o \left(t - \frac{vx}{c^2} \right), \quad (37)$$

which is the general solution to the initial value problem. It represents a time flow as a time-traveling wave in the direction of increasing t with speed given by (35).

5.3 The general solution of the inverse space advection equation

Next consider equation (27),

$$\frac{\partial x}{\partial \tau} - v \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi} = 0.$$

and the initial condition,

$$x(\xi, 0) = x_o(\xi).$$

Following the previous procedure, we find that x is constant along the characteristic curves,

$$\xi + v\tau = \nu, \quad (38)$$

with ν being the constant of integration. Then, the general solution of the inverse space advection equation is,

$$x = x_o(\xi + v\tau). \quad (39)$$

It represents a space flow as a space-traveling wave in the direction of decreasing ξ with a speed equal to v .

5.4 The general solution of the inverse time advection equation

Finally, consider equation (29),

$$\frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi} - \frac{v}{c^2} \frac{\partial t}{\partial \tau} = 0$$

and the initial condition,

$$t(0, \tau) = t_o(\tau).$$

Then, t is constant along the characteristic curves,

$$\tau + \frac{v\xi}{c^2} = \mu, \quad (40)$$

with μ being the constant of integration. These conditions give the general solution to the initial value problem,

$$t = t_o \left(\tau + \frac{v\xi}{c^2} \right), \quad (41)$$

which represents a time flow as a time-traveling wave in the direction of decreasing τ with speed $\frac{v}{c^2}$.

The set of equations (34) and (37) is a mapping of a point with coordinates (x, t) , to a point with coordinates (τ, ξ) . Then, the corresponding equations (39) and (41) are the inverse mapping of a point with coordinates (τ, ξ) to a point with coordinates (x, t) , when they satisfy the conditions set by the Inverse Function Theorem. We call a mapping with an inverse in the context of relativity a transformation.

6 The general linear solutions of the advection equations

In the previous section, we applied arbitrary initial conditions to obtain the general solutions of the space and time advection equations and their inverses. As we saw, those solutions have the form of spatial and temporal transformations, but to qualify for that, they should satisfy the conditions of the Inverse Function Theorem. In that context, we now impose that theorem as a confining condition to the form of the general solutions.

The Inverse Function Theorem states that, for a one-one and onto, continuously differentiable transformation in a certain neighborhood, the inverse of the derivative of the transformation equals the derivative of its inverse,

$$D^{-1}T = DT^{-1},$$

provided the inverse of the derivative of the transformation exists.

The derivative of the transformation T given by equations (34) and (37) is,

$$DT = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial t} & \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial t} & \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \tau_o}{\partial t} & \frac{\partial \tau_o}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial \xi_o}{\partial t} & \frac{\partial \xi_o}{\partial x} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{d\tau_o}{d\alpha} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} & \frac{d\tau_o}{d\alpha} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x} \\ \frac{d\xi_o}{d\beta} \frac{\partial \beta}{\partial t} & \frac{d\xi_o}{d\beta} \frac{\partial \beta}{\partial x} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{d\tau_o}{d\alpha} & -\frac{v}{c^2} \frac{d\tau_o}{d\alpha} \\ -v \frac{d\xi_o}{d\beta} & \frac{d\xi_o}{d\beta} \end{pmatrix},$$

where, α and β are the arguments of equations (37) and (34), respectively. The determinant of the derivative of the transformation is,

$$\Delta = \frac{d\tau_o}{d\alpha} \frac{d\xi_o}{d\beta} \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right).$$

Then, the inverse derivative exists if $\Delta \neq 0$. Thus, $\frac{d\tau_o}{d\alpha} \neq 0$ and $\frac{d\xi_o}{d\beta} \neq 0$, which means that $\tau_o(\alpha)$ and $\xi_o(\beta)$ must be strictly monotonic in the domain of definition of the transformation. Then,

$$D^{-1}T = \frac{1}{\frac{d\tau_o}{d\alpha} \frac{d\xi_o}{d\beta} \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{d\xi_o}{d\beta} & \frac{v}{c^2} \frac{d\tau_o}{d\alpha} \\ v \frac{d\xi_o}{d\beta} & \frac{d\tau_o}{d\alpha} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (42)$$

Parentetically, $x_o(\eta)$ and $t_o(\zeta)$ in the transformation $(\xi, \tau) = (x_o(\eta), t_o(\zeta))$, where η and ζ are correspondingly the arguments of equations (39) and (41), must also be strictly monotonic functions by the same argument. Thus, instead of first calculating the inverse of the derivative of $(\xi_o(\beta), \tau_o(\alpha))$, we could start by calculating the inverse of the derivative of $(x_o(\eta), t_o(\zeta))$. In that case, the determinant is,

$$\Delta' = \frac{dt_o}{d\eta} \frac{dx_o}{d\zeta} \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right),$$

and $\Delta' \neq 0$ implies that the functions $x_o(\zeta)$ and $t_o(\eta)$ must be strictly monotonic.

The derivative of the inverse transformation T^{-1} is,

$$DT^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial t}{\partial \tau} & \frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi} \\ \frac{\partial x}{\partial \tau} & \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial t_o}{\partial \tau} & \frac{\partial t_o}{\partial \xi} \\ \frac{\partial x_o}{\partial \tau} & \frac{\partial x_o}{\partial \xi} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{dt_o}{d\eta} & \frac{v}{c^2} \frac{dt_o}{d\eta} \\ v \frac{dx_o}{d\zeta} & \frac{dx_o}{d\zeta} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (43)$$

On equating the coefficients of matrices $D^{-1}T$ and DT^{-1} , we obtain the non-linear system of first-order ordinary differential equations,

$$\frac{d\tau_o}{d\alpha} \frac{dt_o}{d\eta} = \frac{d\xi_o}{d\beta} \frac{dt_o}{d\eta} = \frac{d\tau_o}{d\alpha} \frac{dx_o}{d\zeta} = \frac{d\xi_o}{d\beta} \frac{dx_o}{d\zeta} = \gamma^2, \quad (44)$$

where,

$$\gamma^2 = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}, \quad (45)$$

is the square of the Lorentz factor.

The system (44) does not have a unique solution. Its solution is of the form $\gamma_1 \gamma_2 = \gamma^2$, where γ_1 and γ_2 are two unknowns. If we set, $\frac{d\tau_o}{d\alpha} = \gamma_1$, then, $\frac{d\xi_o}{d\beta} = \gamma_1$, and consequently, $\frac{dt_o}{d\eta} = \gamma_2$ and $\frac{dx_o}{d\zeta} = \gamma_2$. Accordingly, the first equation,

$$\frac{d\tau_o}{d\alpha} = \gamma_1$$

has the general solution,

$$\tau_o(\alpha) = \gamma_1 \alpha + const. = \gamma_1 \left(t - \frac{vx}{c^2}\right) + \tau_o(0),$$

$$\tau(x, t) = \gamma_1 \left(t - \frac{vx}{c^2} \right) + \tau_o(0). \quad (46)$$

The second equation,

$$\frac{d\xi_o}{d\beta} = \gamma_1$$

has the general solution,

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_o(\beta) &= \gamma_1 \beta + \text{const.} = \gamma_1(x - vt) + \xi_o(0), \\ \xi(x, t) &= \gamma_1(x - vt) + \xi_o(0). \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

The third equation,

$$\frac{dt_o}{d\eta} = \gamma_2$$

has the general solution,

$$\begin{aligned} t_o(\eta) &= \gamma_2 \eta + \text{const.} = \gamma_2 \left(\tau + \frac{v\xi}{c^2} \right) + t_o(0), \\ t(\xi, \tau) &= \gamma_2 \left(\tau + \frac{v\xi}{c^2} \right) + t_o(0). \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

Finally, the fourth equation,

$$\frac{dx_o}{d\zeta} = \gamma_2$$

has the general solution,

$$\begin{aligned} x_o(\zeta) &= \gamma_2 \zeta + \text{const.} = \gamma_2(\xi + v\tau) + x_o(0), \\ x(\xi, \tau) &= \gamma_2(\xi + v\tau) + x_o(0). \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

The set of equations (46)-(49) are linear solutions of the respective advection equations (25), (22), (27) and (29). They are not transformations since the integration constant in each solution is not in the same coordinate system as the independent variables.

We observe that a factor γ_1 multiplies the equations with dependent variables τ and ξ while a factor γ_2 multiplies the equations with dependent variables t and x . This difference expresses the current distinction between space and time measurements performed in the stationary reference frame and the same measurements performed in the moving one.

The following section shows that an additional consideration of the space and time measurement in inertial reference frames eliminates such a distinction by obtaining γ_1 equal to γ_2 . Hence, it establishes the equivalence of inertial reference frames in measuring space and time of events and concurrently derives an extended set of Poincare transformations.

7 The equivalence of inertial reference frames and the extended Poincare transformations

Consider a stationary inertial reference frame K and another frame k moving relative to it with speed v . Additionally, consider a third frame, k' , having the same speed as k relative to K . Consequently, the frame k' is stationary to k [1]. Further, if a point in K has coordinates (x, t) , then, by equations (46) and (47) it has coordinates (ξ, τ) in k , given by,

$$\tau(x, t) = \gamma_1 \left(t - \frac{vx}{c^2} \right) + \tau_o(0), \quad (50)$$

$$\xi(x, t) = \gamma_1(x - vt) + \xi_o(0). \quad (51)$$

If the same point has coordinates (x', t') in k' then it has coordinates (x, t) in K ,

$$t(x', t') = \gamma_1 \left(t' + \frac{vx'}{c^2} \right) + t_o(0), \quad (52)$$

$$x(x', t') = \gamma_1(x' + vt') + x_o(0). \quad (53)$$

The first set of equations in matrix form is,

$$\begin{pmatrix} \tau \\ \xi \end{pmatrix} = \gamma_1 \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\frac{v}{c^2} \\ -v & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} t \\ x \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \tau_o(0) \\ \xi_o(0) \end{pmatrix} \quad (54)$$

and the second set in the same form is,

$$\begin{pmatrix} t \\ x \end{pmatrix} = \gamma_1 \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \frac{v}{c^2} \\ v & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} t' \\ x' \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} t_o(0) \\ x_o(0) \end{pmatrix} \quad (55)$$

Then, on substituting equation (55) into (54) we obtain the transformation from the frame k' to k ,

$$\begin{pmatrix} \tau \\ \xi \end{pmatrix} = \gamma_1^2 \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} t' \\ x' \end{pmatrix} + \gamma_1 \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\frac{v}{c^2} \\ -v & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} t_o(0) \\ x_o(0) \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \tau_o(0) \\ \xi_o(0) \end{pmatrix} \quad (56)$$

Since frame k' is stationary to k the coordinates (ξ, τ) are identical to the coordinates (x', t') . This condition means, first, the matrix factor in the first term of (56) times γ_1^2 must equal the identity matrix,

$$\gamma_1^2 \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

On equating the matrices in this expression, we obtain,

$$\gamma_1 = \pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}.$$

By substituting this value in (45), we obtain,

$$\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 = \pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \equiv \gamma_{\pm}.$$

Second, the sum of the second and third terms in equation (56) must equal zero. On substituting γ_{\pm} for γ_1 in this term and equating to zero, we have,

$$\gamma_{\pm} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\frac{v}{c^2} \\ -v & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} t_o(0) \\ x_o(0) \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \tau_o(0) \\ \xi_o(0) \end{pmatrix} = 0,$$

which gives,

$$\tau_o(0) = -\gamma_{\pm} \left[t_o(0) - \frac{vx_o(0)}{c^2} \right], \quad (57)$$

$$\xi_o(0) = -\gamma_{\pm} [x_o(0) - vt_o(0)]. \quad (58)$$

We solve equations (57) and (58) in terms of $t_o(0)$ and $x_o(0)$ and obtain,

$$t_o(0) = -\gamma_{\pm} \left[\tau_o(0) + \frac{v\xi_o(0)}{c^2} \right], \quad (59)$$

$$x_o(0) = -\gamma_{\pm} [\xi_o(0) + v\tau_o(0)]. \quad (60)$$

If we substitute (57) and (58) in (46) and (47) respectively, and set $\gamma_1 = \gamma_{\pm}$, we obtain,

$$\tau(x, t) = \gamma_{\pm} \left\{ [t - t_o(0)] - \frac{v[x - x_o(0)]}{c^2} \right\}, \quad (61)$$

$$\xi(x, t) = \gamma_{\pm} \{ [x - x_o(0)] - v[t - t_o(0)] \}. \quad (62)$$

If we substitute equations (59) and (60) in (48) and (49), respectively, and set $\gamma_2 = \gamma_{\pm}$, we obtain,

$$t(\xi, \tau) = \gamma_{\pm} \left\{ [\tau - \tau_o(0)] + \frac{v[\xi - \xi_o(0)]}{c^2} \right\}, \quad (63)$$

$$x(\xi, \tau) = \gamma_{\pm} \{ [\xi - \xi_o(0)] + v[\tau - \tau_o(0)] \}. \quad (64)$$

When solving equations (61) and (62) for (x, t) , and using (59) and (60) for the transformation of the initial values, we obtain equations (63) and (64). Conversely, when solving equations (63) and (64) for (ξ, τ) and using (57) and (58) for the transformation of the initial values, we obtain equations (61) and (62). Furthermore, since all equations are polynomials of the first order, they are continuously differentiable, one-one, and onto in the real numbers, thus satisfying the conditions of the Inverse Function Theorem. Also, as strictly monotonic functions, they fulfill the additional requirements for the inversion of their derivatives. Thus, equations (61) and (62) satisfy the conditions for transformations between inertial reference frames with inverses being equations (63) and (64), and vice versa.

For γ_{\pm} taking positive values, the transformation given by (61) and (62), and their inverse given by (63) and (64), are the Poincare transformations with both the time and space origin translated in the same equation. Furthermore, since those transformations also admit negative values of γ_{\pm} , they form a set of extended Poincare transformations.

As we saw in section (6), the factors γ_1 and γ_2 distinguish between moving and stationary frames by multiplying the respective transformations. Then, their equality means that space and time measurement does not discern stationary and moving reference frames. That implies firstly, a reference frame k moving relative to another K measures the space and time coordinates of a static event relative to the coordinates K measures for the event, by transformation equations (61) and (62). Secondly, the reference frame K equivalently measures the coordinates of the event now relatively moving to it by transformation equations (63) and (64).

8 The characteristic curves of the extended Poincare transformations

This section determines the characteristic curves of the extended Poincare transformations. In the previous two sections, we transformed the general non-linear solutions of the advection equations' system to linear ones by the requirement that they are coordinate transformations and their inverses. Further, by the symmetry of the measurement process, we established that those transformations should be equivalent between inertial reference frames. The final solutions (61)-(64) contain arbitrary constants which express the origin's translation of one reference frame relative to another. Thus, the arbitrariness of the initial functions for the solutions has become the arbitrariness in the assignment of the inertial reference frame's origin coordinates. Then, the initial function of the original characteristic curve (36) in transformation (61) consists of a multiplying factor γ_{\pm} plus a constant given by (57). Since (57) is a constant, we may express the characteristic curve (36) in the form as,

$$t - \frac{vx}{c^2} = \lambda' = \lambda + \left(t_o(0) + \frac{vx_o(0)}{c^2} \right),$$

or

$$[t - t_o(0)] - \frac{v[x - x_o(0)]}{c^2} = \lambda \quad (65)$$

Then, this is another form of the characteristic curve along which the transformation (61) remains constant. Correspondingly, we can obtain the respective characteristic curves of the remaining transformations (62)-(64)

as,

$$[x - x_o(0)] - v[t - t_o(0)] = \kappa, \quad (66)$$

$$[\tau - \tau_o(0)] + \frac{v}{c^2}[\xi - \xi_o(0)] = \nu, \quad (67)$$

$$[\xi - \xi_o(0)] + v[\tau - \tau_o(0)] = \mu. \quad (68)$$

The extended Poincare transformations are solutions of the advection equations, constant along their characteristic curves, and thus represent space and time waves with invariant phases along the curves. Additionally, since each transformation equation has a positive and a negative multiplying constant factor equal to γ_{\pm} , it represents a pair of waves with invariant amplitude and opposite phases.

9 Discussion

The current study derived the Space and Time Continuum Model, a formulation of relativistic kinematics founded on a local measurement of space and time. An essential element of the space and time-measurement process is clock synchronization at a distance using light signals. We demonstrated that clock synchronization could only occur in homogeneous and isotropic media. Consequently, if the law of inertia is valid in those media, we can define inertial reference frames that consist of synchronized clocks that locally map an event's position and time measurement into Cartesian axes.

In modeling the measurement of space and time between inertial reference frames, we demonstrated that the synchronized clocks of one frame are measured as non-synchronized by another. Additionally, to this historic finding [1], an inertial frame measures a distance in another frame, along its line of motion, unequally in opposite directions.

The previous results formulated four space and time measurement finite relations in and between inertial reference frames. The homogeneity and isotropy of space gave two of those relations that correspond to the bidirectional space equality and clock synchronicity in an inertial reference frame. Additionally, we derived the other two relations regarding bidirectional distance inequality and clock non-synchronicity between inertial reference frames.

The derivation of the Space and Time Continuum Model as an initial value problem incorporating four space and time advection equations resulted from limiting values of the four conditions above. Their non-linear solutions describe space and time flow as traveling waves. From another mathematical perspective, those solutions have the form of space and time transformations and their inverses. Subsequently, since we independently produced the advection equation solutions, we used their transformation perspective to impose confining conditions on their form.

The resulting solutions are linear and incorporate arbitrary integration constants representing the translation of the space and time origin between inertial reference frames. However, the general linear solutions reflect the present spatial and temporal measurement formulation and distinguish between stationary and moving inertial reference frames. Further consideration of the measurement process eliminated that distinction and demonstrated the equivalence of inertial reference frames in measuring space and time through the extended Poincare transformations. Finally, we derived the characteristic curves of those transformations.

The extended Poincare transformations are a unique outcome of the space and time model. They admit an interpretation as pairs of space and time waves with constant amplitude and opposite constant phases along their characteristic curves. The space transformation represents a space wave transiting at a speed that we usually conceive as the rate of change of space with time. On the other hand, the time transformation has a unique representation as a time wave whose speed denotes the time change rate with space.

A remarkable feature of the Space and Time Continuum Model is the quantitative formulation of space and time flow that results from local space and time measurements in inertial reference frames. The process involves the limit of a bidirectional space and time-measurement of distant events resulting in an infinitesimal synchronization that locally defines the space and time of events. Being infinitesimal, we may apply it in more

general measurement situations to produce more inclusive models of space and time that would correspond directly to local measurement and hence, would be interpretive and explicit in terms of space and time flow.

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